

Monitoring Strategies for Floating Wind Turbines / D2.3

WP2, T2.3

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Executive summary

This report is deliverable D2.3 within the SUsustainable resilient Data-enabled Off-shore wind farm and control CO-design (SUDOCO) project, which aims to develop the "Control Room of the Future" for offshore wind farms. Specifically, this deliverable addresses the challenges and approaches in high resolution monitoring of Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWTs).

FOWT monitoring presents unique challenges due to the harsh offshore environment, inaccessibility, and economic constraints. Reliable, cost-effective, and scalable monitoring solutions are essential, particularly for mooring systems and cables, where current technologies are lacking. Previous studies have shown that virtual sensing with digital twins – inferring unmeasured system states from available measurements – is the most promising solution to address these challenges. Therefore, the state-of-the-art digital twin methods, including physics-based, data-driven, and hybrid approaches, are reviewed as potential solutions.

Physics-based models, especially Kalman filters, offer advantages in virtual sensing, sensor fusion, and interpretability. Data-driven models like neural networks show promise in virtual sensing and anomaly detection but face challenges in training data generation and interpretability. A key finding is the critical importance of system parameter identification for maintaining digital twin accuracy over the lifetime of the FOWT. A sensitivity study highlighted that changes in mooring system parameters significantly impact load observability, necessitating regular model parameter updates. Physics-based models are well-suited for this task due to their straightforward parameter updating capabilities.

In conclusion, while all digital twin approaches have merits, physics-based approaches, particularly Kalman filters combined with data-driven system parameter identification methods, appear most promising for long-term, reliable, and cost-effective FOWT monitoring within the SUDOCO project.

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Abbreviations

ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CM	Condition Monitoring
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CTV	Crew Transfer Vessel
DEL	Damage Equivalent Load
DGPS	Differential Global Positioning System
DLC	Design Load Case
DNV	Det Norske Veritas
FEED	Front End Engineering Design
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HMPE	High Modulus PolyEthylene
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
INS	Inertial Navigation System
IPB	In-Plane Bending
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KRLS	Kernel Regularized Least Squares
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
LRD	Load Reduction Device
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MRU	Motion Reference Unit
NREL	United States National Renewable Energy Laboratory
OPB	Out-of-Plane Bending
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
OMA	Operational Modal Analysis
PINN	Physics Informed Neural Network
RAO	Response Amplitude Operator
RMSPE	Root Mean Square Percentage Error
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
RTTR	Real-Time Thermal Rating
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SLOW	Symbolic Low-to-medium Order Wind turbine model
SUDOCO	SUstainable resilient Data-enabled Offshore wind farm and control CO-design
TF-ARX	Transmittance Function Autoregressive with Exogenous Input
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TLP	Tension Leg Platform
VAR	Vector Autoregressive

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1 Introduction

The objective of the SUDOCO project is to develop the **Control Room of the Future**, which will enable real-time optimization of wind farm performance by considering both power production and structural health of turbines throughout their operational lifetime. This optimization aims to improve both economic and environmental metrics.

Within the scope of SUDOCO, this deliverable specifically addresses the floating wind sector by focusing on high-resolution monitoring solutions for FOWTs. In the context of the control room of the future, comprehensive monitoring of a floating wind farm is a fundamental prerequisite for effective farm operation.

Monitoring forms the basis for assessing the current condition of a wind farm and is essential for predictive maintenance and risk-based inspections, thereby reducing the number of required on site activities. Additionally, there is uncertainty regarding the applicability of International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) load cases—used in the design of FOWTs—over their entire operational lifetime, see Robertson et al., 2019. Continuous monitoring mitigates this risk, improving both insurability and bankability of floating wind projects.

This report outlines the requirements and challenges associated with monitoring FOWTs both in general and specifically for each major component of a FOWT, including the turbine, platform, tower, moorings, and cables. It highlights the need for reliable, cost-effective and scalable high-resolution monitoring solutions given the inaccessibility, harsh environment, and cost sensitivity of floating wind turbines. However, such technologies are not yet available on a large scale for FOWTs, especially for mooring systems.

Previous studies, such as Cevasco et al., 2022, have identified virtual sensing through digital twins as the most promising approach to address these challenges. Virtual sensing means deriving unmeasured system states from other signals, e.g. inferring mooring loads from the position and orientation of the floater. Accordingly, this report presents and compares state of the art digital twin methodologies for FOWT monitoring. To provide a basis for comparison, an overview of relevant system properties is first provided. Then, the different digital twin methods are introduced and analyzed, including approaches based on physics-based models, data-driven models, and hybrid models.

A comparative review of traditional component specific monitoring technologies is not provided here, as this has already been done, e.g. by Schwarzkopf et al., 2020 and specifically for mooring monitoring, see Ford et al., 2020.

Current research focuses primarily on monitoring under constant conditions, neglecting the effects of aging and degradation. To address this gap, this report investigates long-term aging effects through a sensitivity study and evaluates the previously discussed monitoring approaches for their suitability for long-term application.

This report serves as a basis for the development of a prototype high resolution monitoring solution for FOWTs within the SUDOCO project.

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2 Challenges and Requirements

An overview of the components of a FOWT can be seen in Figure 2.1. The requirements and challenges of the monitoring of the components will be discussed and reviewed in the following sections.

Figure 2.1: Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT) component overview.

2.1 Definition of high-resolution monitoring

In the context of FOWT monitoring, the terms Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) and Condition Monitoring (CM) are commonly employed. Schwarzkopf et al., 2020 summarized their definitions as follows:

- Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) is defined as the process of implementing a damage identification strategy for aerospace, civil, and mechanical engineering infrastructure (Ren, 2017). It serves as remote diagnosis of (civil) infrastructure by evaluating recorded sensor signals.
- Condition Monitoring (CM) is the procedure of monitoring the state of different parameters in electrical and rotating machinery (vibration, temperature,

noise, etc.) in order to identify discrepancies between the actual and the nominal state and to identify changes which indicate a development of faults and inefficiencies (Schwarzkopf et al., 2020).

Schwarzkopf et al., 2020 state that terms SHM and CM are often used synonymously in practice, causing confusion and misunderstanding.

Therefore, for the purpose of this deliverable, monitoring is understood to include the following tasks, in addition to the scope above.

1. Detect damages and failures.
2. Provide indicators for upcoming damages or failures.
3. Detect changes and anomalies in system properties.

Monitoring of structural extreme loads requires a historical collection of extreme values (i.e. storm event responses). Monitoring of structural fatigue requires time-domain or frequency-domain signals in a rather high resolution to capture all relevant vibration modes, which underscores the need for high-resolution monitoring. Usually a rainflow-counting algorithm is applied to time-domain signals, see Lotsberg, 2016.

Load monitoring usually happens with some delay and not in strict real time. The implementation strategy depends on the functional safety requirements, especially if load monitoring outputs are used within the controller safety system.

2.2 Standards

Standards for monitoring of FOWTs include the Det Norske Veritas (DNV), IEC and International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards:

- ISO 17359:2018 and ISO 13372:2012 provide general guidelines for implementing CM and SHM for machines, not specifically for FOWTs (ISO, 2018, ISO, 2012).
- IEC 61400-13:2015 outlines procedures for measuring and analyzing mechanical loads on wind turbines (IEC, 2015).
- IEC 61400-25 addresses the communication protocols necessary for monitoring and controlling wind turbines (IEC, 2017).
- DNVGL-ST-0119 focuses on the structural design of FOWTs. It also includes considerations for in-service inspection and monitoring as part of the overall structural integrity management (DNV, 2021b).

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- DNVGL-ST-0126 addresses risk-based inspections of offshore wind farms (DNV, 2021c).
- DNV-SE-0439 outlines the requirements for certifying CM systems for wind turbines (DNV, 2021a).

2.3 General challenges and requirements

One of the primary challenges in monitoring FOWTs arises from the extreme environmental conditions and remote locations in which they operate. Sensors, which form the foundation of monitoring systems, are subjected to harsh weather conditions, saltwater corrosion, and substantial mechanical loads, particularly in subsea environments. Over the turbine's operational lifetime, these factors increase the risk of sensor failure. Sensor maintenance, along with the inherently required inspections of the FOWT, presents significant challenges due to restricted accessibility. In contrast to onshore wind turbines, the inspection of FOWTs necessitates specialized logistical arrangements, often involving helicopters or Crew Transfer Vessels (CTVs). Moreover, seasonal weather patterns impose constraints on the available time windows for on-site operations, while the continuous movement of the floating platform further limits workability. The substantial distance from shore, frequently greater than that of bottom-fixed offshore turbines, further makes maintenance and inspections more complex, and increases operational costs.

Beyond technical and logistical constraints, economic considerations play a pivotal role in FOWT monitoring. The floating offshore wind industry operates within a highly cost-sensitive environment, demanding the minimization of expensive on-site activities to enhance economic feasibility.

Given these challenges, a monitoring solution for FOWTs must be cost effective, reducing both sensor related and maintenance costs. Despite the harsh environmental conditions, the system must be highly reliable and accurate to minimize the frequency of on-site inspections and provide the information needed to operate the wind farm. In addition, it must be scalable to allow installation and operation on numerous FOWTs within a farm.

2.4 Component-specific challenges and requirements

A FOWT merges two distinct industries, namely the offshore and the wind turbine industry. Both industries come with their standards and supply chains for their respective technologies. FOWTs build on the high Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of both industries but face challenges due to the required integration, division of responsibilities between stakeholders, and deviating requirements.

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The aspects to be considered for FOWT monitoring in this report are summarized in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT) monitoring scopes.

2.4.1 Turbine

In general, methods from bottom fixed turbines can be applied. Additional challenges due to floating substructures include the motion-induced loads due to the platform motions. Increased tilt angles and acceleration limits need to be monitored to ensure functionality and health of components in the nacelle, e.g. hydraulic pumps. However, this can usually be achieved with Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs), already available on the nacelle.

The accessibility of FOWTs is different from bottom-fixed turbines, such that large-component replacement can be challenging (Bayati and Efthimiou, 2023; Pérez Moreno et al., 2024; Scheu et al., 2018). Consequently, it is crucial to employ advanced failure predictions to enable early planning of such operations.

2.4.2 Platform including tower

The platform and tower include monitoring of the structural deformation using strain gauges, which are in accordance with civil engineering standards, see Schwarzkopf et al., 2020. However, replacing or supplementing these with alternative methods to measure hull and tower loads could help reduce the uncertainty and cost related to strain gauges.

Offshore engineering equipment such as active ballast and bilge systems typically have their own monitoring system and may also feature active feedback controllers.

2.4.3 Mooring system

Mooring systems typically consist of various steel wire, polyester or nylon ropes, and chains, equipped with clump weights, buoyancy tanks, and potential Load Reduction

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Devices (LRDs) (Sørum et al., 2023). LRDs are additional mechanical elements, which aim to reduce peak and fatigue loads of the mooring system. Secondary outfitting equipment, so-called jewellery, such as chain-stoppers, in-line tensioners, connectors, shackles, H-plates, and tri-plates can introduce faults (Harvey et al., 2024; Jump, 2021).

A comprehensive review of (mostly) oil and gas mooring failures of floating platforms can be found in Fontaine et al., 2014. The paper reports various failure modes: Fatigue appears to be the most common cause of mooring failures, followed by installation, mechanical, and corrosion-related failures. See Lone et al., 2021 for a comparison of fatigue and corrosion effects. Anomalies and failures in the mooring system are difficult to detect, especially for highly redundant mooring systems see (Gumley et al., 2016; Gumley et al., 2019; Jayasinghe et al., 2022; Killbourn et al., 2021).

Chain fatigue is categorized into tension-tension fatigue as well as In-Plane Bending (IPB) and Out-of-Plane Bending (OPB), both primarily induced by inter-link friction (Martinez Perez et al., 2018). Accurately assessing fatigue damage necessitates the load history in time-domain or frequency-domain for each mooring line. In offshore wind applications, this requires continuous data collection over several decades. The most intuitive approach is to measure mooring tensions using load cells or strain gauges positioned near the fairlead or chain stopper, i.e. where forces are exerted on the structure. However, subsea sensors are inherently prone to failure due to the harsh marine environment, demanding regular maintenance or a redundant instrumentation strategy, both of which reduce economic viability. As a result, alternative methodologies, such as indirect load measurements, must be explored.

The properties of a mooring line generally change over its lifetime, due to creep and changes in static and dynamic stiffness of ropes, as well as marine growth. The static and dynamic stiffness of synthetic ropes depends on past extreme loads (Lone et al., 2022; Pham et al., 2019; Mullet et al., 2012; Petruska et al., 2010)

Various anchor technologies exist with the most common being drag embedment and piled anchors. The uncertainty of the as-installed anchor position is significantly larger for drag embedment anchors, which can cause unmodeled behavior of the mooring system.

In summary, monitoring the integrity and fatigue of mooring systems is essential for the safe and reliable operation of FOWTs. Yet, the development of an economically viable monitoring solution remains an ongoing challenge.

2.4.4 Cable

The cable consists of the array cable and the export cable. The connections to the FOWT are usually done via a dynamic cable with a lazy-wave or other elas-

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tic shapes, making the cable as flexible as possible without introducing critical fatigue loads (Janocha et al., 2024). The same technology is generally necessary for bottom-fixed wind turbines, but the larger amplitude of motion of FOWTs has to be accounted for.

Thus, fatigue and extreme load effects are comparable to mooring loads and generally difficult to monitor, as discussed in Section 2.4.3.

However, compared to moorings, there are more technologies available to monitor cable condition. Techniques such as Real-Time Thermal Rating (RTTR) and partial discharge monitoring allow condition assessment without the need for additional sensor equipment along the cable. In addition, the use of fiber optic sensors allows direct monitoring of spatial deformation, providing valuable insight into cable health and performance over time. The reader is referred to the COREWIND.EU project for further reading (Schwarzkopf et al., 2020).

2.5 Uncertain system properties

There can be significant discrepancies between the designed and the as-built FOWT for various system properties. For example, the natural frequencies and Response Amplitude Operators (RAOs) of the FloatGen demonstrator show differences between measured and simulated values, as shown in Choynet et al., 2018. Such deviations can be caused by manufacturing tolerances, installation conditions, or environmental influences and affect the overall performance and behavior of the floating structure.

Accurately determining these properties is a significant challenge and must be incorporated as a dedicated step during the commissioning phase, especially if the monitoring system relies on system parameters as input.

2.6 Aging and degradation

Various system properties of a FOWT change significantly throughout its lifetime. An example from bottom-fixed wind turbines is scour, which can significantly alter global bending modes. (DNVGL, 2016)

An automated or semi-automated system identification methodology, such as Operational Modal Analysis (OMA) is required to keep the operator and the monitoring system aware of such changes.

The influence of changing system properties of moorings is analyzed through a simulation study in Chapter 4.

Degradation models in reliability engineering are usually based on stochastic process models. These are not specifically addressed in this report.

3 State of the Art of Monitoring through Virtual Sensing with Digital Twins

Monitoring through virtual sensing with digital twins, unlike component-specific monitoring, focuses on monitoring the entire FOWT or its subsystems as an integrated system. This approach leverages a digital twin – a virtual replica of the physical asset that integrates sensor data with a system behavior model – to provide real-time insights into the asset’s state, including its loads.

This chapter introduces digital twin-based approaches for FOWT monitoring. It begins by presenting the general concept of digital twins and their application to monitoring, followed by an overview of their key properties as a basis for comparing different methodologies. The chapter then presents the different approaches along three main categories: physics-based models, data-driven models, and hybrid models that combine both. Finally, the chapter concludes with a discussion of the suitability of these approaches for long-term FOWT monitoring, based on a sensitivity study on aging parameters in digital twin models for mooring lines.

As shown in Chapter 2, a major challenge for monitoring of FOWTs are the moorings. Therefore, the analysis in this chapter will focus on the moorings, although a holistic approach is applicable to all previously discussed components of a FOWT.

3.1 General concept and typically used sensor data

The core concept of a digital twin for FOWT monitoring involves the creation of a model that accurately represents the system behavior of the FOWT or its subsystem. In order to match the state of the real asset with the model, it is continuously updated with data from sensors installed on the FOWT, enabling to monitor the FOWT’s response to external forces such as wind, waves, and currents, as well as varying operational conditions. By mirroring the physical asset in the virtual realm, the digital twin facilitates a real-time understanding of the turbine states including its loads and thus enables to run analysis to monitor its structural health and integrity. Figure 3.1 provides an illustration of the digital twin concept for FOWTs.

In the context of monitoring of FOWTs a digital twin relies on a suite of sensors to capture the FOWT’s motion and the surrounding environmental conditions. Typically employed to capture the global response of the asset are IMUs in the

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Figure 3.1: Illustration of the digital twin concept. Source: Courtesy of Akselos

floaters and nacelles to measure the turbine’s angular rate, inclination, and acceleration, which allows, through an integration of the signals (Inertial Navigation System (INS)), to provide data on its rotational and translational motion. In the context of navigation applications these systems are often referred to as Motion Reference Units (MRUs). Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSSs) offer precise positioning information, enabling tracking of the FOWT’s horizontal position and orientation. To incorporate the turbine states into the digital twin, Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) data can be used to retrieve signals like the rotor speed. Strain gauges are often installed to measure bending of the tower or strain within the floater. Some approaches assume additional measurements of the environmental conditions, such as Light Detection And Ranging (LiDAR) to capture the wind speed and direction, or Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) to measure currents or wave radars to obtain wave measurements.

A key feature of the digital twin approach is its ability to perform indirect measurement, or virtual sensing, of signals that are challenging or expensive to measure directly. The model of the digital twin derives unmeasured states or parameters of the FOWT by using the available signals through its understanding of the systems behavior. For instance, the mooring line loads, crucial for assessing fatigue and predicting failures (see Section 2.4.3), can be virtually sensed by using the accurate position and orientation of the floater. This eliminates the need for costly and unreliable subsea sensors, offering a more robust and cost-effective solution for mooring line monitoring. Overall, the virtual sensing capability reduces costs through the digital twin’s reliance on fewer and less maintenance-intensive sensors. In addition, it enhances the monitoring systems robustness by the ability to compensate sensor

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failures temporarily.

Another important feature, which the majority of digital twin approaches provide, is sensor fusion. Sensor fusion is the process of combining data from multiple sensors to create a more accurate and comprehensive picture of the system's state. It leverages the complementary strengths of different sensors while mitigating their individual limitations, resulting in more robust and reliable measurements. This is particularly important for FOWTs, where the dynamic environment and the complex interactions between the turbine, the floater, and the mooring system can make it difficult to obtain reliable measurements from individual sensors. By integrating data from multiple sensors into its model, the digital twin can reduce sensor noise by accounting for system behavior and leveraging the strengths of each sensor. This results in more reliable estimates of the system's state. For example INSs are very accurate in measuring the translational acceleration and velocity but the position signal drifts, whereas GNSS position signals are not prone to drift but provide poorer velocity measurements.

The provision of holistic real-time monitoring of the FOWT through the digital twin, including loads, is the basis for performing further analyses such as fatigue assessments, which enables monitoring in a cost-effective manner with respect to Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditures (OPEX).

3.2 Overview of digital twin features

This section aims to provide an overview of the properties that a digital twin model may possess. By doing so, it offers a foundation for the classification of the various available approaches. Figure 3.2 offers an overview of the properties of digital twins for FOWT monitoring.

3.2.1 Primary model

The core of any digital twin is its primary model, which determines how the system processes and interprets received input data. Data-driven models rely on statistical and machine learning techniques, such as regression and neural networks, to infer system behavior directly from observed data patterns. In contrast, physics-based models rely on established physical principles from disciplines like fluid dynamics and structural mechanics. The models are then built with methods such as simulations, transfer functions, and Kalman filters to derive system responses based on governing equations. Physics Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) and transfer function fitting represent a hybrid approach that integrates physics-based constraints into data-driven learning.

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Figure 3.2: Overview of properties of digital twins for FOWT monitoring.

The outputs generated by a primary model of the digital twin dictate the type of information it provides for decision making. These outputs may include system parameters that track long-term changes in structural characteristics, virtually sensed system states that estimate unmeasured conditions from measured signals, and filtered system states that enhance clarity by reducing measurement noise, which can be used for further postprocessing. Certain primary models can directly provide material fatigue assessments and issue failure alarms. Very valuable additional outputs are uncertainty quantification and data integrity flags, as they help operators to assess the reliability of the estimations and sensor readings.

3.2.2 Postprocessing methods

In order to gain more insights from the outputs, various postprocessing methods are employed. Condition inference techniques utilize identified system parameters to evaluate structural health, while phase-resolved system states enable advanced fatigue analysis methods, such as rainflow counting and peridynamic fatigue tracking. These approaches allow for a detailed assessment of accumulated damage over time. Additionally, comparisons between expected (healthy) and actual responses

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of the system provide insights into degradation patterns or detect anomalies like failures. Furthermore, degradation models extend these capabilities by offering predictive insights into long-term wear and failure probabilities, allowing for proactive maintenance planning.

3.2.3 Uncertainty driver

Despite their capabilities, digital twins must account for inherent uncertainties arising from different kind of sources. For data-driven models, one key source of uncertainty is the quality and quantity of the training data. Modeling uncertainty stems from simplifications and approximations used in system representations, while parametric uncertainty arises from unknown or varying material properties, environmental conditions, and operational factors. Measurement uncertainty, introduced through sensor inaccuracies, further complicates the reliability of FOWT monitoring.

3.2.4 Sensor noise filtering methods

Sensor signals are the basis to align the digital twin with the real asset. However, they are subject to noise and outliers, which can be partly mitigated through sensor noise filtering methods. If the used digital twin model has no inherent capabilities to remove noise, only classical filtering techniques, such as low-pass filtering, are applied before feeding them into the primary model. Alternatively, other models can perform sensor data fusion to combine multiple data sources to enhance accuracy and robustness. In addition, model-based filtering leverages system dynamics to refine measurements and reduce inconsistencies. These techniques are essential to the reliability of the digital twin, especially in fatigue monitoring.

3.2.5 Root cause tracking

An important feature of FOWT monitoring is to determine the root cause of provided failure alarms. The suitability of different approaches for this task varies due to their differing methodologies. Highly suited white-box models, which rely on well-defined physical principles and equations, provide full interpretability. Grey-box models integrate empirical data with theoretical frameworks, thus their internal states' interpretability is limited. Black-box models, which are primarily data-driven, often lack interpretability, making them less suitable when traceable root cause is required.

3.2.6 Retuning of models

To maintain accuracy over time, the models within the digital twins must be retuned to changing system behavior, such as mooring line elongation. This can be accomplished by directly implementing the aged parameters into the model, which is

typically done for physics-based models. However, for data-driven models, retraining must be performed on an updated dataset in order for machine learning-based models to adapt to the new system behavior. Section 4 addresses this aspect specifically.

3.2.7 Application

The broad spectrum of applications for digital twins in the context of FOWT monitoring highlights their importance in enabling the effective operation of FOWTs. One of the most critical applications is failure detection, which enables timely interventions to prevent catastrophic structural failures. For instance, the timely detection of a mooring line failure is essential for triggering an emergency turbine shutdown, preventing excessive drift and potential damage to the infrastructure. Metrics for benchmarking failure detection approaches include time to detection, which measures the responsiveness of the system in identifying failure events, and the false positive rate and false negative rate, which evaluate the accuracy and reliability of failure predictions to minimize unnecessary shutdowns or missed failures.

Material fatigue assessment allows operators to monitor the progressive degradation of structural components, optimizing maintenance and inspection schedules to reduce OPEX and extend operational lifespans while minimizing downtime. The key metric for benchmarking fatigue monitoring approaches would include Damage Equivalent Load (DEL) accuracy, which ensures that the loads are accurately estimated. Load limit monitoring enables risk-based inspections of floating wind farms, as it allows targeted inspections of units that exceeded the limits after a severe event, such as a storm. Anomaly detection identifies deviations from expected behavior, providing early warnings of potential defects or unforeseen operational issues. Furthermore, performance monitoring, such as LiDAR-based power performance monitoring, enables operators to obtain insights that can be applied to increase the efficiency of both existing and future wind farms. The approaches for the last applications are typically benchmarked based on the key metric Root Mean Square Percentage Error (RMSPE) to evaluate their accuracy.

3.3 Physics-based modeling approaches

One group of approaches to implementing a model within a digital twin is the use of physics-based models. These models simulate the phase-resolved dynamics of a FOWT using numerical methods, based on physical principles, relying on mathematical equations to describe the relationships between different system states. By doing so, they allow the prediction of how a FOWT will behave under any conditions within the validity range of the model. Widely recognized physics-based models in the FOWT domain include OpenFAST from United States National Renew-

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able Energy Laboratory (NREL) and Symbolic Low-to-medium Order Wind turbine model (SLOW) from the University of Stuttgart and sowento.

3.3.1 Simulation

A straightforward approach to integrating physics-based models into digital twins is to use measured input data to run simulations, either at a global system level or for local subsystems. By using such simulations, virtual sensing can be achieved, allowing for the estimation of system states that may not be directly measurable.

Numerical simulations of FOWTs are generally accurate enough to provide predictions of most quantities and have extensively been tested and reviewed in past works (Eça and Hoekstra, 2014; Müller and Cheng, 2016; Robertson et al., 2018; Desmond et al., 2019; Lemmer et al., 2019; Robertson et al., 2020; Robaux et al., 2022; Dighe et al., 2023; Kretschmer et al., 2025).

Global simulations of FOWTs typically require environmental inputs such as wind and wave characteristics, which are challenging to measure accurately in the time domain. Motion-induced noise contaminates raw sensor data, necessitating robust preprocessing to extract reliable parameters. As a result, the accuracy and applicability of these simulations hinge on effective noise mitigation techniques before the data ever enters the model.

Simulation-based approaches generate virtually sensed system states and the corresponding loads as functions of those states. Postprocessing techniques, such as fatigue tracking methods, leverage these simulation results to estimate long-term structural degradation. When measured outputs are available, direct comparisons can be made between the expected healthy system response and the actual measured response. However, uncertainties can arise from modeling, parametric, and measurement sources (Lemmer et al., 2019). Because simulation-based models do not inherently incorporate state measurements as inputs, they lack built-in sensor noise filtering or sensor fusion. In consequence, they require classical filtering methods during preprocessing to ensure reliable inputs. On the other hand, their full physical representation of internal states provides complete transparency for root cause tracking, making them a white-box solution. Retuning is also relatively straightforward, as adjustments can simply be made by modifying the relevant model parameters.

Applications of simulation-based approaches in monitoring include, in principle, fatigue monitoring and load limit monitoring. Although no specific applications for FOWTs have been presented, methodologies developed for bottom-fixed wind turbines could potentially be adapted. For example, Pagitsch et al., 2020 developed a model to simulate rotor loads, gear forces, bearing forces, bearing temperatures, and power losses using SCADA and design data.

3.3.2 Transfer functions

An alternative method for integrating physics-based models into digital twins is the use of transfer functions, which mathematically describe the relationship between system states. Transfer functions allow for the estimation of unmeasured system outputs, based on known relationships with measured inputs. By applying a transfer function to a measured input variable, an unmeasured output can be computed, enabling virtual sensing without the need for direct measurement of all system states.

The properties, such as outputs and root cause tracking capabilities, of transfer function-based approaches closely align with those of simulation-based approaches, discussed in Section 3.3.1.

In the context of FOWTs, Pimenta et al., 2024 applied this concept to estimate tower bending moments and fatigue life consumption. Their physics-based model utilized readily available tower top accelerations, eliminating the need for strain gauges. By establishing a transfer function between tower top accelerations and tower bending moments, they accurately estimated internal forces and fatigue damage using only existing monitoring systems.

3.3.3 Limits and thresholds

The concept of limits in monitoring relies on deriving measurable thresholds from physics-based models to determine when critical conditions or component failures occur. By defining these thresholds, limits can be used to detect exceedances that indicate either impending failure or a component that has already failed. For example, specific displacement values beyond a predefined threshold can indicate excessive structural deformation or failure.

The primary outputs of threshold-based approaches include failure alarms and warnings that provide clear indications when critical operational thresholds are exceeded. In addition, uncertainty quantification can potentially be incorporated by assessing confidence in measurements and model accuracy.

Due to their direct reliance on detection of threshold violations, limit-based methods are not well suited for advanced postprocessing techniques.

Uncertainty in limit-based approaches arises from modeling, parametric, and measurement uncertainty. The accuracy of the predefined thresholds depends on the fidelity of the underlying physics-based model and the certainty of the parameters used. The output itself depends on the reliability of the sensor measurements used for monitoring.

Limit-based approaches do not inherently include noise filtering. If necessary, classical filtering techniques must be applied during preprocessing to ensure that sensor noise does not lead to false alarms or missed detections.

A key advantage of threshold-based approaches is their full interpretability, as

they are purely physics-based. This means that root cause tracking is straightforward, classifying them as a white-box method.

Retuning of threshold-based approaches involves redefining the critical thresholds as needed. However, since these thresholds are determined through physics-based modeling, updates can be directly implemented by adjusting the parameters in the underlying model.

Applications of threshold-based approaches in monitoring include failure detection, load limit monitoring, and anomaly detection. For example, Minnebo et al., 2014 implemented a basic watch circle approach to detect mooring line failures using Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS), triggering alarms when a floating structure moved beyond predefined boundaries. Touzon et al., 2019 further advanced this principle by introducing more sophisticated watch circle contours, enhancing the accuracy of mooring failure detection. Additionally, threshold-based methods can be used for load limit monitoring by defining maximum permissible stresses and displacements, enabling early warnings before structural integrity is compromised.

3.3.4 Kalman filter

More sophisticated and common is the integration of physics-based models in a digital twin with classical state observer methods from control theory, such as the Kalman filter (Kalman, 1960) or the Luenberger observer (Luenberger, 1966). In the context of wind energy, Kalman filters have been applied in many applications, but predominantly other than global digital twins (Ammerman et al., 2024; Branlard et al., 2020; Jayasinghe et al., 2023; Branlard et al., 2023; Vondelen et al., 2023).

The Kalman filter, initially introduced by Kalman, 1960, is an algorithm designed to achieve optimal solutions through the least squares method for state estimation in linear systems. This algorithm combines available measurements and knowledge about the system behavior, all the while taking both modeling uncertainty (process noise) and measurement noise considerations into account.

The basic operating mechanism of the Kalman filter, as shown in Figure 3.3, involves several key steps:

1. Kalman filter makes predictions about the output $\hat{y}(k)$, based on linear model of the system (A, B, C, D , e.g. derived from a simulation software) where q^{-1} is the integrator.
2. Predictions are compared to the actual measured outputs $y(k)$.
3. Disparity between the predicted and measured outputs, denoted $\Delta y(k)$, is calculated.

4. Disparity $\Delta y(k)$ is used as a basis to correct the predicted states $\hat{x}(k)$. The correction is achieved by applying the Kalman Gain $K(k)$ (generated by the Kalman filter algorithm), resulting in the refined states $\tilde{x}(k)$.
5. Determination of the Kalman Gain $K(k)$ depends on considerations of the expected noise inherent in both the model predictions and the measurements, and the relationship between the states included in the model. Thus, not only directly measured states are corrected, but rather all states that are related to the measurement, depending on their relationship described in the model.

Figure 3.3: General structure of the linear Kalman filter. Source: Marchthaler and Dingler, 2017

Since its initial publication in 1960, the Kalman filter has given rise to numerous subtypes, such as the Extended Kalman filter for nonlinear systems. However, all subtypes share the principle of the prediction and correction step cycle. The Luenberger observer (Luenberger, 1966) relies on the same general principle, with the key distinction lying in the determination of the gain matrix, which is used to correct the prediction with the measurements.

Typical outputs are virtually sensed and filtered system states, with inherent uncertainty quantification using error covariance matrices. This makes them particularly suitable for applications requiring reliable state estimation.

In terms of post-processing, they facilitate fatigue tracking methods such as rain-flow counting with S-N curve analysis and peridynamic fatigue tracking. In addition, the use of multiple Kalman filters with different models and sensor inputs enables comparisons between healthy and actual system responses, as well as dynamic limit setting and monitoring.

Uncertainty in Kalman filter-based approaches arises from modeling inaccuracies, parametric uncertainties, and measurement noise.

Kalman filters excel at filtering sensor noise by facilitating sensor fusion and physical model-based noise filtering, making them highly effective for digital twin applications.

Their interpretability for root cause tracking is a significant advantage, as they operate as white-box models that provide full transparency into their state estimation process and full interpretability of each internal state as they are physically.

Retuning these models is straightforward, as updated parameters can be incorporated directly into the filter equations.

Kalman filter-based approaches in monitoring are, in principle, suitable for any of the typical applications. For failure detection, Kalman filters can be used to estimate the expected system response in the absence of failures and compare it with actual sensor measurements. For mooring lines, one approach is to estimate the platform position using a Kalman filter that does not rely on displacement measurements (e.g., using SCADA data). The estimated position can then be compared to actual measurements to detect deviations beyond expected limits, indicating mooring line failure. This approach was implemented by Jayasinghe et al., 2023 using a Luenberger observer for mooring failure detection. In addition, multiple Kalman filters simulating different failure scenarios (e.g., each individual mooring line failing) can be run in parallel, and the best-matching scenario can help identify which line has failed. For material fatigue assessment, virtually sensed loads estimated by the Kalman filter can be used for fatigue tracking. Jayasinghe et al., 2023 applied this approach for mooring line fatigue, while Branlard et al., 2023 developed a digital twin using a Kalman filter to estimate tower section loads, enabling tower fatigue monitoring. Their method was validated using numerical simulations and full-scale prototype data from the TetraSpar demonstrator (Borg et al., 2020). For load limit monitoring, Kalman filters can be used to track virtually sensed loads and determine whether they exceed predefined thresholds. Ammerman et al., 2024 used a Kalman filter to estimate states such as platform displacements and tower bending in real time and validated their results against on a scaled prototype. While they did not explicitly apply this to load limit monitoring, their approach could be extended for this purpose. In principle, anomaly detection could be implemented by comparing the estimated healthy system response with actual measurements over time, while performance monitoring could be achieved by analyzing the observed states. However, no specific FOWT implementations have been introduced yet.

3.4 Data driven model approaches

Data-driven approaches identify patterns and relationships within collected data to model system behavior without explicitly incorporating physical laws. These models utilize statistical techniques, machine learning—including neural networks—to extract insights from measured or simulated data. Either historical and/or simulation data is used to train the model prior to deployment, or the model continuously integrates measurement data during operation to detect changes in system behavior.

A significant advantage of data-driven methods is their relatively low barrier to entry due to their inherently straightforward workflow. The required data is typically obtainable from standard sensors, or alternatively can be generated from the usually available simulation models of the FOWT, e.g. in OrcaFlex. This enables the efficient generation of data sets that allow the application of data-driven methods without requiring in-depth knowledge of the physical behavior of the system. However, while the initial steps are accessible, developing robust and high-performing models often becomes considerably more complex, especially when it comes to preparing the data in a way that captures the relevant system behavior, choosing suitable algorithms, validating the results, and understanding what the models are actually learning.

The primary uncertainty drivers of prior to deployment trained data driven models are the quantity and quality of the training data. Therefore, these aspects, among others, are discussed separately in detail in Section 3.4.1 before the different modeling approaches are introduced in the subsequent sections.

3.4.1 Generation of training data

The generation of high-quality training datasets is crucial for data-driven models, as it forms the foundation of their capabilities.

Training data can be derived from historical measurements recorded on the asset and is easily accessible when standard sensors can be used. However, a key limitation of this approach is that only a limited range of environmental conditions are typically recorded, resulting in an incomplete representation of system responses. Due to the complex behavior of FOWTs, generalization from such limited datasets is often infeasible. An exception exists for isolated linear relationships, where limited data may suffice to obtain accurate system responses. For example, McCauley et al., 2025 demonstrated that linear methods are applicable to the relationship between floater motion and tower bending. Fundamentally, when using measurement data, it is essential to assess its uncertainty, ensuring that it accurately captures the effects of interest. This includes considerations of accuracy, sampling rate, bias and other relevant factors.

Alternatively, coupled simulations can be used to generate training data sets

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to cover a wider range of environmental conditions and corresponding system responses. Simulation tools such as OpenFAST or OrcaFlex are commonly used for this purpose. However, additional uncertainties arise from modeling fidelity and parametric uncertainty, making it critical to validate the simulation model against real-world data to ensure the appropriateness of the data generated. For details on simulation model validation methods, see Singh et al., 2024; Kretschmer et al., 2025; Knezevic et al., 2022; Popko et al., 2021; Bussemakers, 2020; Desmond et al., 2019; Robertson et al., 2020; Müller and Cheng, 2016; Driscoll et al., 2016.

Once a validated model is available, simulation cases must be selected to comprehensively represent the entire range of environmental conditions. An additional source of parametric uncertainty arises from potential inaccuracies in the assumed environmental conditions. This issue has been similarly discussed in the context of IEC load cases, where the representativeness of the assumptions has been questioned, e.g. on wind characteristics by Robertson et al., 2019. In particular, incorrect wave spectra and wind characteristics assumptions can significantly affect the results. A notable example is the sensitivity study on the peak shape parameter of the wave spectrum conducted by Müller et al., 2018 within the LIFES50+ project. Their study showed that for a particular peak shape factor, a sudden increase of approximately 10% in tower and mooring DELs occurred, likely due to a design sensitivity with respect to the wave spectrum. If such effects are not present in the training datasets, data driven models likely fail to reconstruct them accurately. Such untrained responses can also be due to various other factors, such as freak waves, swell, wind shear, wind turbulence, wind veer, etc., all of which need to be considered when creating the training database.

Furthermore, Müller et al., 2018 analyzed the required selection of the general environmental conditions: Wind speed, significant wave height, wave period, and their directions. Overall, they found that it is relevant to cover not only the range of individual parameters, but also numerous combinations, since the interaction between the parameters is significant. In particular, they found that the wave periods inducing the highest loads on FOWTs vary depending on the wave direction. This implies that a single wave period cannot be assumed as the worst-case scenario for all directions. Their study concluded that selecting wave periods, based solely on occurrence probability (e.g., 10th percentile, mean, and 90th percentile), may lead to non-conservative results by neglecting critical events. Regarding wave heights, their impact was found to be significant and highly dependent on the interplay of environmental factors, including wind speed, wave period, and wave direction. The sensitivity of loads to wind speed and direction shows the necessity of covering all load ranges within the training dataset. Additionally, the importance of wind and wave misalignment was emphasized, with Müller et al., 2018 recommending analysis with at least 15 deg variation steps. This is particularly relevant as real-world

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Figure 3.4: LIFES50+ OO-Star Wind Floater Semi 10 MW DEL bootstrap evaluation (wind and wave varying): median values after consideration of n_{sim} values. Red horizontal lines indicate median, box borders 95th percentile and whiskers 99th percentile values. Source: Müller et al., 2018

measurements show misalignment angles can exceed 50 deg in offshore regions, especially during extreme events (Shanahan and Fitzgerald, 2025). Furthermore, it is important to note that the effect of wind wave misalignment varies based on platform type. For instance, Tension Leg Platforms (TLPs) may be particularly sensitive to a 90-degree wind-wave misalignment due to the lack of aerodynamic damping.

In addition to the environmental conditions, the operational status of the turbine, e.g. normal operation, idling, or parked, must be considered and represented in the training data set.

Also, Müller et al., 2018 highlighted the importance of simulation convergence for accurate load assessment, specifically the number of seeds required to obtain stable results. Figure 3.4 presents the results of a bootstrap analysis of fairlead, tower, and blade DELs, illustrating the need to run multiple seeds to achieve convergence. Moreover, the inclusion of wave excitations in addition to turbulence and wakes typically requires around 12 seeds (rather than just 6) to fully capture low-frequency platform motions and ensure stable load estimates.

Furthermore, when deploying digital twins across an entire wind farm, variations in the individual properties of each unit may necessitate distinct training datasets for each unit. A sensitivity analysis investigating the influence of the parameters listed in Table 4.2 on mooring load observability through floater motions revealed

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significant differences between units within the farm. A 10 m error in the mooring anchor spread radius due to installation inaccuracies leads to an error of up to 75 % in the fairlead DEL, and a 10 m error in the assumed water depth due to bathymetry leads to an error of up to 15 % in the fairlead DEL. For a detailed description of the methodology and study setup, refer to Section 4.1.

Overall, the creation of a training database using simulation data is generally possible and a substantial amount of relevant results is typically available through the Front End Engineering Design (FEED) process. However, significant challenges remain in ensuring that all relevant system responses are covered within the dataset. Especially the high sensitivity of loads with respect to environmental conditions, with its multi-dimensional parameter space, leads to a large amount of required simulations. Consequently, this results in an extensive training database and any missing system responses contribute to increased uncertainty.

3.4.2 Regression

Regression analysis is a fundamental statistical and machine learning technique used to model the relationship between two or more variables. It aims to establish functional dependencies between input and output variables in order to predict, quantify, or analyze underlying patterns in data. Basic forms of regression include linear regression, polynomial regression, and least squares regression. In the context of FOWTs, more advanced regression methods are usually used, such as Vector Autoregressive (VAR) models.

Typical outputs of regression models in FOWT digital twin applications include estimates of long term changes in system parameters. When combined with pre-defined thresholds or limits determined by other methods, alarms or warnings can also be triggered to signal potential structural integrity concerns.

Regression models are primarily used for anomaly detection, identifying deviations from expected or initial system behavior. When combined with appropriate post-processing methods, they are also intended to be used for material fatigue assessment. The major advantage of this approach would be that it does not require the direct measurement of the fatigue driving loads, not even virtually, but only the identification of system parameters.

The primary uncertainty driver in regression-based monitoring approaches is measurement uncertainty. Additional uncertainties may be introduced during post-processing, depending on the methodology employed. These uncertainties can include modeling assumptions, data preprocessing choices, and threshold setting strategies.

Regression models are inherently focused on detecting trends in the data rather than responding to short-term fluctuations. As a result, they are robust to sensor

noise and can effectively handle noisy data over long periods of time. However, they do not directly provide short-term filtering capabilities for real-time noise reduction.

In terms of root cause tracking, the application of regression falls between grey box and white box, depending on the application. If there is a clear, interpretable relationship between measurements and output, it is a white box, such as a simple trend in measurements. If the regression model is very complex, with many variables, it may be difficult to determine the root cause, making it a grey box.

Regression models generally do not require retuning because they are designed to capture long term trends, i.e. detecting these changes. However, depending on the specific implementation, it may be necessary if there are dependencies on other parameters, in which case a simple update of the parameters is usually sufficient.

The system parameters identified by the regression models are often intended to serve as input for further post-processing to infer the structural health of the FOWT from the detected changes. The objective is to infer the condition of the asset from parameter changes that can serve as indicators. Anastasiadis et al., 2024 employed VAR and Transmittance Function Autoregressive with Exogenous Input (TF-ARX) models to detect changes in mooring stiffness through vibration analysis, providing the inputs for further post-processing to gain insight into the health of synthetic mooring lines.

Similarly, Walker et al., 2021 applied Kernel Regularized Least Squares (KRLS) regression to identify long term deviations between "healthy" short-term predictions - obtained using a neural network - and actual system measurements. Their results highlight the potential of regression-based methods for detecting structural degradation. However, while the detection of long term changes has shown promising results, further research is needed to develop and validate robust post-processing techniques for condition inference.

Moreover, regression models can also be used as surrogate models to determine unmeasured states more efficient from measurements of environmental conditions (Ludot et al., 2025).

3.4.3 Neural networks

Neural networks are a class of machine learning models inspired by the structure and function of the human brain. They consist of interconnected layers of artificial neurons that process input data and extract complex patterns to generate outputs. The training process of a neural network typically involves feeding it large amounts of labeled data, adjusting the weights of the connections between neurons using optimization algorithms that minimize a predefined loss function to improve prediction accuracy. This iterative process, known as backpropagation, allows the network to learn from errors and refine its ability to generalize to new, unseen data.

Common types of neural networks include feedforward neural networks, which

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Figure 3.5: Structure of the LSTM neural network seq2seq. Source: Gräfe et al., 2024

are primarily used for straightforward mapping between inputs and outputs without internal state or memory, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) typically used for spatial data processing like images and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) for sequential data.

RNNs are specifically designed to handle sequences by incorporating a "memory" mechanism. This allows them to use past information to influence current processing steps. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, a type of RNNs, address the limitation of traditional RNNs, which struggle with long-term dependencies. LSTMs incorporate gating mechanisms that regulate information flow, enabling them to selectively remember or forget information over long sequences, making them particularly suitable for modeling complex systems such as FOWTs.

An example of a LSTM neural network is shown in Figure 3.5 from Gräfe et al., 2024. It is designed to predict time series data by taking a sequence of input time steps and processing them through multiple layers, including LSTM layers to capture temporal dependencies. The model outputs a sequence of load estimations corresponding to the input sequence.

Neural networks are highly flexible and can provide virtually any output, from virtually sensed and filtered system states to long-term changes in system parameters. Neural networks can also be trained to directly estimate further processed outputs such as material fatigue condition or failure alarms and warnings. However, standard methods usually do not include uncertainty quantification. Various post-processing techniques can be applied to neural network outputs, as these models are capable of generating a diverse range of outputs. These include fatigue tracking methods, dynamic limit determination and monitoring, and degradation models.

Uncertainty in neural network-based models is primarily influenced by the quantity and quality of the training data. For more details on training data generation, see Section 3.4.1. In addition, sensor measurement uncertainty also contributes to the overall uncertainty within the digital twin.

The sensor noise filtering capabilities of neural networks are noteworthy because they can perform sensor fusion using multiple data sources as input. In addition,

they are capable of model-based noise filtering using their internally trained model.

Root cause analysis in neural networks is challenging because of their "black box" nature. Unlike interpretable models, neural networks do not provide direct insight into how specific input features influence their outputs, which can make troubleshooting and understanding decision-making processes difficult.

Retuning of neural networks usually involves further training on an expanded or updated dataset.

Due to the flexibility of neural networks, their range of applications is wide. For failure detection, neural networks have been applied to mooring lines, as demonstrated by Gumley et al., 2016, with further improvements introduced by Jayasinghe et al., 2022. In addition, they have been used to monitor cable protection systems by Duth et al., 2024. In anomaly detection, Stadtmann and Rasheed, 2024 used neural networks to identify deviations in structural behavior indicative of potential faults. Fatigue monitoring of mooring lines has also shown promising results, including direct output of DELs and load time series further post-processed by Gräfe et al., 2024. Studies by Santos et al., 2020 have used neural networks to estimate thrust as a precursor to fatigue analysis, while Sharma and Nava, 2024 have focused on identifying long-term changes and classifying damage in mooring lines.

While neural networks have demonstrated promising results across various applications, their testing has been limited. Many studies use the same simulation environment to generate both training and testing data, potentially neglecting system responses not covered in the training data. These limitations, discussed in Section 3.4.1, highlight the need for further research on the suitability of neural networks in real-world applications.

3.5 Hybrid model approaches

Hybrid models combine data-driven techniques, such as machine learning, with physics-based principles to enhance predictive accuracy and generalization. These models leverage physical laws to constrain learning, ensuring consistency with known scientific principles while benefiting from the flexibility of data-driven methods.

3.5.1 Physics informed neural networks

PINNs extend traditional neural networks by incorporating physical laws directly into the loss function. This is achieved by embedding governing equations, such as differential equations describing structural dynamics, into the training process. By enforcing physical constraints, PINNs ensure that the learned model not only fits the data but also adheres to known physical principles, improving reliability.

The training process for PINNs can be more computationally expensive than standard neural networks, as solving the physics-based loss function often involves

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complex differential equations that require additional computational effort. However, the advantage of this approach is improved generalization to unseen data, as the network learns both from measured observations and from the underlying physics governing the system's behavior.

Typical outputs of PINNs include virtually sensed and filtered system states.

In terms of postprocessing, these networks facilitate fatigue tracking methods and enable the comparison of a healthy versus an actual system response, as well as dynamic limit determination and monitoring.

Uncertainty in PINNs arises from several sources. As with conventional neural networks, the quantity and quality of training data affect prediction accuracy, although PINNs tend to be less sensitive to data sparsity due to their physical constraints. However, additional uncertainty is introduced by modeling assumptions and parametric variations in the physical part of the loss function, which can affect the reliability of predictions.

PINNs retain the strong sensor noise filtering capabilities of conventional neural networks, while benefiting from improved model-based filtering through the incorporation of physical laws.

Retuning of PINNs is achieved by additional training on new data, similar to standard neural networks. However, the retuning effort can be reduced because the physical parameters embedded in the loss function can be adjusted directly, allowing faster adaptation to changing conditions.

Applications of PINNs in monitoring of FOWTs include material fatigue assessment and load limit monitoring, as these networks can generate detailed time series of structural responses. For example, Santos et al., 2023 used a PINN to estimate fatigue loads in the tower transition piece, demonstrating its effectiveness in capturing structural stress variations. Similarly, Yung et al., 2025 developed a physics-guided spatial-temporal graph neural network as a surrogate model for computationally efficient tower force estimation. Beyond fatigue monitoring, PINNs can also be used for failure and anomaly detection by comparing predicted healthy system responses with actual measurements using multiple models.

3.5.2 Transfer function fitting

Transfer function fitting is a method of characterizing the relationship between an input and an output by deriving a mathematical model, based on observational data. Although data-driven, it is fundamentally guided by physical principles, particularly in the selection of an appropriate transfer function model. Knowledge of system behavior, such as linearity, time invariance, and expected response characteristics, plays a critical role in defining the model structure. This ensures that the derived transfer function is not only statistically optimized, but also physically meaningful. As a result, transfer function fitting is capable of virtual sensing applications in digital

twins.

The typical outputs are virtually sensed system states.

Fatigue tracking methods can be applied as a postprocessing step. If output measurements are available, comparison of healthy vs. actual system response is possible.

Uncertainty in transfer function fitting is influenced by the quantity and quality of training data, although less data may be required if a linear relationship is assumed. In addition, modeling uncertainty and measurement uncertainty contribute to the overall accuracy when applying the model.

Sensor noise filtering is not inherently included in transfer function fitting, so classical filtering methods must be applied in preprocessing.

In terms of root cause tracking, this approach is considered a gray box method because the model structure is predefined based on physical knowledge, but the parameters are identified from the data.

Retuning the model usually requires retraining on a new dataset.

The main application of transfer function fitting is fatigue assessment. McCauley et al., 2025 presented an approach to extract the relationship between tower bending moments and floater motions in the TetraSpar demonstrator (Borg et al., 2020). They found that the transfer function between pitch/roll motions and bending moments remains linear even under extreme conditions, allowing for a fitted linear transfer function. In principle, anomaly detection and failure detection could be achieved by comparing the estimated healthy system response with the actual data. However, specific implementations in these areas have not yet been presented.

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4 Evaluation of Long Term Feasibility of FOWT Monitoring via Sensitivity Study

Both physics-based and data-driven approaches demonstrate promising potential for monitoring of FOWTs. However, current research primarily evaluates these approaches under constant conditions, leaving one important challenge unaddressed: the operational lifetime of FOWTs: Over time, component aging leads to changes in system behavior, such as mooring line creep. Thus, the digital twin model initially created with as-built parameters will become increasingly inaccurate as the system ages. Additionally, environmental conditions are expected to shift due to climate change, necessitating the consideration of their impact on FOWT behavior, e.g. sea water level rise.

4.1 Sensitivity study on aging parameters in digital twin models for mooring lines

To gain further understanding of the time-dependent effects, a sensitivity study is conducted to assess the influence of variations in system parameters on fatigue loads using the mooring system as an example. Since most mooring digital twins rely on floater motion measurements to estimate mooring loads, this principle is replicated. The study mimics an ideal digital twin by feeding unperturbed motion data from an OpenFAST (NREL, 2021) simulation into MoorDyn, the mooring module within OpenFAST, to compute the resulting mooring loads. This approach effectively replicates an almost ideally functioning virtual sensing process for mooring loads as no noise is applied and a proven mooring model is fed with its required inputs.

To evaluate the sensitivity of this approach to parameter variations, two digital twins are established: one with the initial model parameters and another with adjusted parameter matching the one used in the "aged" OpenFAST simulation, where the varied parameter is applied. The influence of model parameter variations on the observability of mooring loads is quantified by comparing the statistics of the virtually sensed mooring load time series from both digital twins like DELs and mean.

Figure 4.1 presents a schematic representation of the general concept for com-

paring modified and unmodified digital twins in the sensitivity study.

Figure 4.1: Concept of digital twin mooring model parameter sensitivity study.

Table 4.1 lists the parameters varied in the sensitivity study. As for the whole SUDOCO project, the simulations utilize the IEA 22 MW reference turbine with a semi-submersible floater (version 1.0.1), which uses a chain-only 3x1 catenary mooring system by Zahle et al., 2024. Environmental conditions are derived from binned hindcast data at Sørlige Nordsjø II (Cheynet et al., 2022). To evaluate the influence of each parameter variation, simulations corresponding to Design Load Case (DLC) 1.2 are conducted. DLC 1.2 refers to a standard operational scenario defined in wind turbine design guidelines, where the turbine operates under normal wind conditions without any faults or shutdowns. This case is used to assess the typical loads experienced during standard operation. The simulations consist of twenty individual runs, each lasting one hour, and together they span the entire operational wind speed range of the turbine. This ensures that the load response across all expected wind conditions is captured for every parameter variation. For each wind speed, a different turbulence seed is used, with half of the simulations using aligned wind and wave directions and the other half using misaligned conditions. The simulations employ OpenFAST version 3.5.1 and its corresponding MoorDyn version.

Table 4.1: Varied parameters in sensitivity study on their influence on observability of mooring fatigue loads.

Parameter	Range	Note
Mooring length	+1%	International Energy Agency (IEA)-22 MW has an chain-only mooring system, which usually does not elongate. However, synthetic moorings, especially High Modulus PolyEthylene (HMPE) ropes are prone to creep. (ABS, 2014) Therefore, mooring elongation is analyzed.
Mooring stiffness	-8%	Change through 10 mm diameter reduction due to expected corrosion in 20 years.
Mooring mass per meter	-8% to +5%	Change through 10 mm diameter reduction due to expected corrosion in 20 years. Change due to 100 mm marine growth. (Spraul et al., 2017)
Mooring diameter	-0.01 m to +0.1 m	Change through 10 mm diameter reduction due to expected corrosion in 20 years. Change due to 100 mm marine growth. (Spraul et al., 2017)
Mooring drag coefficient	±0.15	Change of surface roughness, size and shape of mooring lines. (Kim et al., 2017)
Water density	-0.25 kg/m ³	Through 5 K water temperature warming.
Water depth	+20 cm	Through global sea level rise.

Figure 4.2 presents the sensitivity of the varied parameters. The relative errors between modified and unmodified digital twins of upwind and downwind fairlead tension are analyzed, specifically DEL and mean values, to assess sensitivity in monitoring fatigue loads. Please note that the error in DEL will lead to an exponentially larger error in the fatigue damage. This is seen in the following equation by Müller et al., 2018 which relates relative damage and relative DEL values:

$$\frac{DEL1}{DEL2} = \left(\frac{D1}{D2}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where D is the damage. Hence, a DEL error of 5% is equivalent to an error in the damage of 1.21 or 21% for materials with SN-curve slope of $m = 4$.

The results of the sensitivity study show that parameters such as mooring length, mooring mass and mooring diameter significantly influence mooring load estimations, with errors up to 40% in DEL. In contrast, the parameters water density,

Figure 4.2: Sensitivity of aging system parameters in the digital twin for estimating mooring loads. Omitted quantities are shown in Figure 4.3.

mooring stiffness (steel chains) and sea water rise, depicted in Figure 4.3, exhibit negligible impact.

Additionally, although not related to the effects of aging FOWTs, the influence of anchor position and bathymetry, i.e. water depth, was analyzed to gain understanding of how sensitive a digital twin model can be between different FOWTs in a wind farm. Table 4.2 presents the analyzed parameter ranges and the results. It shows significant differences between the parameter variations for both mooring anchor position and bathymetry. Section 3.4.1 provides a broader context to those results.

In conclusion, the sensitivity study confirms the necessity of updating the digital twin model over the operational period to ensure reliable mooring load observability. This necessity is divided into two main tasks: first, identifying changes in system parameters, and second, implementing these changes in the digital twin model.

Figure 4.3: Sensitivity of aging system parameters in the digital twin for estimating mooring loads.

4.2 System parameter identification

System parameter identification is the process of detecting changes in system properties over time that influence the system behavior. The most intuitive approach to do this is direct inspection of the FOWT to measure parameters such as marine growth or mooring length. Alternatively, regular measurement campaigns can be conducted to measure the virtually sensed signal directly, e.g., with load cells installed on moorings, to detect deviations that can be used to infer parameter changes using regression methods, as Liu et al., 2024 does. Both approaches are methodologically quite intuitive but are economically mostly not viable due to the associated costs of expensive equipment and on-site activities. One measure to counteract the costs is that the findings of changes may be applied to neighboring turbines in a wind farm and thus reduce the overall costs.

In contrast, online identification utilizes previously measured signals to infer changes in system behavior. For instance, analyzing the relationship between wind speed and platform deviations can reveal long-term trends. Data-driven methods,

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Table 4.2: Varied parameters in sensitivity study on their influence on observability of mooring fatigue loads between units in wind farm.

Parameter	Range	Note	Upwind fair-lead DEL error	Mean upwind fairlead tension error
Mooring anchor spread radius	± 10 m	Difference between units in farm through anchor installation inaccuracies.	+75% to -50%	+23% to -21%
Bathymetry	± 10 m	Difference between units in wind farm through bathymetry.	-15% to -5%	+15% to -5%

such as regression or neural networks, are well suited for this task. Examples include inverted neural networks for updating finite element beam models Noever-Castelos et al., 2021 and regression-based methods for identifying mooring stiffness changes (Anastasiadis et al., 2024).

OMA is another method for detecting changes in system behavior. This technique identifies natural frequencies, mode shapes, and damping ratios using ambient forces like wind and waves, eliminating the need for artificial excitation. The obtained findings can be used to detect changes in the system and thus derive changed parameters. An illustrative application employing physics-based models is the Kalman filter-based stochastic subspace identification method, as utilized by Vondelen et al., 2023 to ascertain the tower natural frequencies and damping of a bottom-fixed turbine.

4.3 Implementation of aged system parameters in digital twin model

The implementation of updated system parameters should ideally be done such that identified changes in parameters are directly used within the model. For example, Liu et al., 2024 introduced an approach that combines system parameter identification through regression with a simulation-based observer to monitor turbine loading. This approach estimates the degradation factor of a static parameter (equivalent inertia) by projecting the deviation between measured and estimated rotor speeds onto a lifted function space using a sinusoidal blending function. The estimated degradation factor is then fed back into the digital twin to update the model parameter, enabling online adaptive calibration and maintaining the digital twin's prediction performance even as the wind turbine degrades.

However, the implementation of the changed system behavior in digital twins has not yet been specifically addressed for floating wind, so integrated approaches are

not yet introduced. Therefore, the suitability to adjust digital twin models to updated parameters is analyzed in general.

For physics-based models, updating parameters is straightforward, as new values can be directly incorporated. This makes them highly suitable for an updating approach. Nevertheless, the acquisition of accurate parameters for different stages of the lifetime of a system or is essential and should not be underestimated. In contrast, phase-resolved data-driven models require retraining on updated datasets to reflect new system behavior. PINNs can reduce retraining effort by incorporating updated parameters into the loss function, though some retraining remains necessary. A possible alternative is designing neural networks with sensitive system parameters as input, eliminating the need for retraining but requiring an extensive initial dataset, covering all parameter possibilities. Data-driven regression models that detect changes in system behavior inherently integrate parameter updates obviously without external intervention.

Overall, while physics-based models typically offer a more straightforward path for integrating updated parameters and can be highly practical for system parameter adjustments, the final choice between physics-based or data-driven strategies ultimately depends on the specific application requirements, data availability, and model fidelity needs.

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5 Conclusion

This report provides an overview of the challenges and requirements for high-resolution monitoring of FOWTs. It highlights the need for reliable, cost-effective, and scalable solutions due to the harsh environment, inaccessibility, and economic constraints of offshore wind. In particular, the monitoring of mooring systems remains a significant challenge, as suitable solutions are still lacking.

Among the various monitoring approaches, data-driven methods such as neural networks have been explored in research and, in principle, have shown great potential for FOWT monitoring, particularly in the areas of virtual sensing, sensor noise handling, and anomaly detection. However, they require large training data sets. Due to the unavailability of sufficient measurement data, these datasets often need to be generated using simulation data. Generating a training database that sufficiently covers all relevant system responses – including the relevant environmental conditions, a sufficient number of seeds to ensure convergence, turbine-to-turbine variations within a wind farm, etc. – remains a major challenge due to its high computational cost. In addition, one major drawback of purely data-driven models is their limited interpretability. Yet, data-driven methods have proven effective in identifying long-term system parameter changes, making them suitable for system parameter identification applications.

Physics-based approaches, in particular Kalman filter-based digital twins, have also been identified as highly suitable for FOWT monitoring, provided sufficiently accurate and up-to-date models can be maintained. Kalman filters can offer robust sensor noise handling through model-based filtering and sensor data fusion, as well as phase-resolved virtual sensing. Once a validated physics-based model of a FOWT is available, these approaches can provide real-time state estimation with full interpretability facilitating root cause analysis and fault diagnosis. It goes without saying that they rely heavily on the fidelity of the underlying model assumptions.

Hybrid approaches aim to leverage the strengths of both data-driven and physics-based methods, potentially reducing reliance on highly detailed models or extensive data sets. Transfer function fitting has shown particular promise for virtual sensing, especially when state relationships between measured and unmeasured variables are linear. In such cases, training data derived solely from measurements may be sufficient, eliminating the need for extensive simulation-based supplementation. However, additional frameworks for handling sensor noise are required to ensure robustness. PINNs provide a balance between data-driven flexibility and physics-based constraints, but they still face the same training data generation challenges

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as purely data-driven approaches.

In addition, this report highlights the critical importance of regularly updating the model within the digital twin to maintain its accuracy over the long operational lifetime of FOWTs. A sensitivity study on aging parameters in digital twin models for mooring loads confirmed this. For example, for the IEA 22 MW reference turbine with catenary mooring system, a 5% error in the mooring mass parameter due to untracked marine growth leads to a 21% error in fatigue damage at the fairlead. Identifying changes in system parameters and implementing them in the digital twin model is therefore essential to maintain accuracy over time. While physics-based models offer straightforward parameter updating mechanisms, data-driven approaches require significant effort to retrain models on an updated training database to reflect changes in system parameters.

In conclusion, each digital twin approach—physics-based, data-driven, and hybrid—brings unique strengths and challenges to the long-term, reliable, and cost-effective monitoring of FOWTs. For instance, the Kalman filter, when combined with system parameter identification, can be a strong candidate for the development of a robust high-resolution monitoring solution within the SUDOCO project, provided its underlying physics-based model is regularly updated. Meanwhile, data-driven and hybrid methods offer complementary benefits, such as flexibility, adaptability, and reduced reliance on model detail, yet may require careful data management and interpretability frameworks.

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